

A Study of India Population Growth Rate Structure in Last 5 Years

Dr. Ganesh Rajendra Walunj¹ & Dr. Balasaheb Sudhakar Wakchaure²

Department of Economics,

S. M. B. S. T. Arts, Science & Commerce College, Sangamner

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ganesh Rajendra Walunj

DOI -10.5281/zenodo.14857260

Abstract:

India 2024 population is estimated at 1,450,935,791 people at mid-year. India population is equivalent to 17.78% of the total world population. India ranks number 1 in the list of countries and dependencies by population. The population of India is expected to increase from 121.1 crores to 151.8 crores during the period 2011-2036 - an increase of 25 percent in twenty-five years at the rate of 1.0 percent annually. As a consequence, the density of population will increase from 368 to 462 persons per square kilometer. A change in the age structure of the population changes the dependency ratio. A group of people between the ages of 0 and 14 who depend on other people for survival are dependent people. The ratio between 15 and 65 of these dependents is the dependency ratio. An increase or decrease in the dependency ratio affects the GDP of a country. GDP increases if the dependency ratio decreases. Population growth deals with the annual change in total population, and is affected by factors such as fertility, mortality and migration.

Keywords: Population, Density, Life Expectancy, Birth Rate & Death Rate.

Introduction:

The population of India as per 2011 census was 1,210,854,977. India added 181.5 million to its population since 2001, slightly lower than the population of Brazil. India, with 2.4% of the world's surface area, accounts for 17.5% of its population. Uttar Pradesh is the most populous state with roughly 200 million people. Over half the population resided in the six most populous states of Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Bihar, West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh of the 1.21 billion Indians, 833 million (68.84%) live in rural areas while 377 million stay in urban areas. 453.6 million people in India are migrants, which is 37.8% of total population.

The population of India is expected to increase from 121.1 crores to

151.8 crores during the period 2011-2036 - an increase of 25 percent in twenty-five years at the rate of 1.0 percent annually. As a consequence, the density of population will increase from 368 to 462 persons per square kilometer. India 2024 population is estimated at 1,450,935,791 people at mid-year. India population is equivalent to 17.78% of the total world population. India ranks number 1 in the list of countries and dependencies by population. The population density in India is 488 per Km² (1,264 people per mi²). The total land area is 2,973,190 Km² (1,147,955 sq. miles). 36.6 % of the population is urban (530,387,142 people in 2024). The median age in India is 28.4 years.

A change in the age structure of the population changes the dependency ratio. A group of people between the ages

of 0 and 14 who depend on other people for survival are dependent people. The ratio between 15 and 65 of these dependents is the dependency ratio. An increase or decrease in the dependency ratio affects the GDP of a country. GDP increases if the dependency ratio decreases. The reasoning behind this is that people aged 15 to 65 will outnumber dependents. Now obviously the number of

working people will be higher when the dependency ratio is lower. So, GDP is higher as the number of working people is higher. So now it is clear that GDP increases when dependency ratio decreases. Population growth deals with the annual change in total population, and is affected by factors such as fertility, mortality, and migration.

1. India Population:

Chart No. 1: India’s Population

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
1.	Population	1,396,387,127	1,407,563,842	1,417,173,173	1,428,627,663	1,441,719,852
2.	Growth Rate	0.96%	0.80%	0.68%	0.81%	0.92%
3.	Compared Years	Increase	Increase	Increase	Increase	Increase

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growt-rate>

The above table shows the India’s population from 1950 to 2024. The United Nations projections are also included through the year 2100. The current population of India in 2024 is 1,441,719,852 a 0.92% increase from 2023. The population of India in 2023 was 1,428,627,663 a 0.81% increase from

2022. The population of India in 2022 was 1,417,173,173 a 0.68% increase from 2021. The population of India in 2021 was 1,407,563,842 a 0.80% increase from 2020. The population of India in 2020 was 1,396,387,127 a 0.96% increase from 2019.

2. India Population Density:

Chart No. 2 India Population Density

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
1.	Population Density	424.79	428.19	431.11	434.60	438.58
2.	Growth Rate	0.96%	0.80%	0.68%	0.81%	0.92%
3.	Compared Years	Increase	increase	increase	increase	increase

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growt-rate>

India population density from 1950 to 2024 of table No. 2. United Nations projections are also included through the year 2100. The current population density of India in 2024 is 438.58 people per square kilometer a 0.92% increase from 2023. The

population density of India in 2023 was 434.60 people per square kilometer a 0.81% increase from 2022. The population density of India in 2022 was 431.11 people per square kilometer a 0.68% increase from 2021. The population density of India in 2021 was

428.19 people per square kilometer a 0.80% increase from 2020. The population density of India in 2020 was

424.79 people per square kilometer a 0.96% increase from 2019.

3. India Urban Population:

Chart No. 3 India Urban Population

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022
1.	Urban Population	465,871,825	476,786,386	487,702,168	498,179,071	508,368,361
2.	Growth Rate	2.36%	2.34%	2.29%	2.15%	2.05%
3.	Compared Years	Increase	increase	increase	increase	increase

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growt-rate>

Urban population refers to people living in urban areas as defined by national statistical offices. It is calculated using World Bank population estimates and urban ratios from the United Nations World Urbanization Prospects. Aggregation of urban and rural population may not add up to total population because of different country coverages. India urban population for

2022 was 508,368,361 a 2.05% increase from 2021. India urban population for 2021 was 498,179,071 a 2.15% increase from 2020. India urban population for 2020 was 487,702,168 a 2.29% increase from 2019. India urban population for 2019 was 476,786,386 a 2.34% increase from 2018. India urban population for 2018 was 465,871,825 a 2.36% increase from 2017.

4. India Rural Population:

Chart No. 4 India Rural Population

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022
1.	Rural Population	903,131,481	906,325,664	908,684,959	909,384,771	908,804,812
2.	Growth Rate	0.44%	0.35%	0.26%	0.08%	0.06%
3.	Compared Years	increase	increase	increase	increase	decline

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growt-rate>

Rural population refers to people living in rural areas as defined by national statistical offices. It is calculated as the difference between total population and urban population. Aggregation of urban and rural population may not add up to total population because of different country coverages. India rural population for 2022 was 908,804,812 a 0.06%

decline from 2021. India rural population for 2021 was 909,384,771 a 0.08% increase from 2020. India rural population for 2020 was 908,684,959 a 0.26% increase from 2019. India rural population for 2019 was 906,325,664 a 0.35% increase from 2018. India rural population for 2018 was 903,131,481 a 0.44% increase from 2017.

5. India Life Expectancy:

Chart No. 5 India Life Expectancy

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
1.	Life Expectancy	69.73	69.96	70.19	70.42	70.62
2.	Growth Rate	0.33%	0.33%	0.33%	0.33%	0.29%
3.	Compared Years	increase	increase	increase	increase	increase

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growth-rate>

India life expectancy from 1950 to 2024 of table No. 5. United Nations projections are also included through the year 2100. The current life expectancy for India in 2024 is 70.62 years a 0.29% increase from 2023. The life expectancy for India in 2023 was 70.42 years a 0.33%

increase from 2022. The life expectancy for India in 2022 was 70.19 years a 0.33% increase from 2021. The life expectancy for India in 2021 was 69.96 years a 0.33% increase from 2020. The life expectancy for India in 2020 was 69.73 years a 0.33% increase from 2019.

6. India Birth Rate:

Chart No. 6 India Birth Rate

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
1.	Birth Rate	17.592	17.377	17.163	16.949	16.750
2.	Growth Rate	-1.20%	-1.22%	-1.23%	-1.25%	-1.17%
3.	Compared Years	decline	decline	decline	decline	decline

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growth-rate>

India birth rate from 1950 to 2024 of table No. 6. United Nations projections are also included through the year 2100. The current birth rate for India in 2024 is 16.750 births per 1000 people a 1.17% decline from 2023. The birth rate for India in 2023 was 16.949 births per 1000 people a 1.25% decline from 2022. The

birth rate for India in 2022 was 17.163 births per 1000 people a 1.23% decline from 2021. The birth rate for India in 2021 was 17.377 births per 1000 people a 1.22% decline from 2020. The birth rate for India in 2020 was 17.592 births per 1000 people a -1.20% decline from 2019.

7. India Death Rate:

Chart No. 7 India Death Rate

Sr. No.	Content	Years				
		2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
1.	Death Rate	7.309	7.344	7.380	7.416	7.473
2.	Growth Rate	0.490%	0.480%	0.490%	0.490%	0.770%
3.	Compared Years	increase	increase	increase	increase	increase

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growth-rate>

India Death Rate from 2020 to 2024 of table No. 6. United Nations projections are also included through the year 2100. The current birth rate for India in 2024 is 7.473 Deaths per 1000 people a 0.770% decline from 2023. The birth rate for India in 2023 was 7.416 Deaths per 1000 people a 0.490% increase from 2022. The birth rate for India in 2022 was 7.380 Deaths per 1000 people a 0.490% increase from 2021. The birth rate for India in 2021 was 7.344 Deaths per 1000 people a 0.480% increase from 2020. The birth rate for India in 2020 was 7.309 Deaths per 1000 people a 0.490% increase from 2019.

Conclusions:

As per Census 2011, India's population was 121.1 Crore with 48.5% female population and the total population is expected to reach to 152.2 crore during 2036 with a slightly improved percentage of female population (48.8). In 2023, the annual population growth in India increased by 0.1 percentage points (+14.71 percent) compared to 2022. Accordingly, 2023 was the first time during the observed period that the population growth has increased in India. The current population of India in 2024 is 1,441,719,852, a 0.92% increase from 2023. The current population density of India in 2024 is

438.58 people per square kilometer a 0.92% increase from 2023. India urban population for 2022 was 508,368,361 a 2.05% increase from 2021. India rural population for 2022 was 908,804,812 a 0.06% decline from 2021. The current life expectancy for India in 2024 is 70.62 years a 0.29% increase from 2023. The current birth rate for India in 2024 is 16.750 births per 1000 people a 1.17% decline from 2023. The current birth rate for India in 2024 is 7.473 Deaths per 1000 people a 0.770% decline from 2023. Population growth deals with the annual change in total population, and is affected by factors such as fertility, mortality, and migration.

Reference Books:

1. Indian economy- Datta & Sundaram
2. Demography, Success Publication
3. भारतीय अर्थव्यवस्था, रसाळ राजेंद्र, सक्सेस प्रकाशन, २०१०

Websites:

1. <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/IND/india/population-growth-rate>
2. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/271308/population-growth-in-india/#statisticContainer>